

Mapping Trends of Geopolitical Research: A Bibliometric Analysis 2000-2021

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Abstract

In recent years, geopolitical research has gained momentum. To fully explore its progress and impact, an extensive overview of research was conducted reviewing all journals in Scopus dataset, examining published research between the periods of 2000 and 2021. Principally, a bibliometric analysis was employed documenting a significant increase in publications in the last five years. Specifically, the journal of Sustainability Switzerland has one of the highest numbers of publications on Geopolitical research. The literature is dominated, principally, by authors from Asia, United Kingdom, United States, Russian Federation, and Germany. The study identified the most frequently cited authors, drawing on a list of co-authorship between authors and cooperation between countries in the field. The predominance of Asian, German, Russian and English publications was prevalent in the networks, centered around their international collaborations. The findings of this study highlighted the lack of mapping and systematic review of existing literature which is a necessary applied component of the social, political sciences, economic, and multidisciplinary studies. Furthermore, Geopolitical research is a multidisciplinary field of inquiry, however, the field gravitate more towards the social sciences with the highest number of publications in GPR, compared to other neighboring disciplines. The results of this study contribute to the existing and prospective literature by shedding light on previously untapped avenues which may immensely enrich any potential enquiry in the field of geopolitical research and practice.

Keywords: trends; geopolitics; research; bibliometric; geo-culture

1. Introduction

Geopolitics is originally a branch of geography that strives to map and explain the relationship between geographical realities and its link to international affairs. Such link between geography and international affairs has been documented dating back to the times of ancient Greeks. However, its reach has been limited and was until the discovery of modern geography's methodological and conceptual tools that theoreticians could examine those connections in an attempt to approximate scientific precision. Consequently, the discipline's mission became transparent. Essentially, it strives to provide an identification of the geographical circumstances that best explain the power dynamics at play, in a study of the character and behavior of nations (S. Spencer 42-47). 'Geo-politics' as a term was coined at the end of the nineteenth century by the Swedish political scientist Rudolf Kjellén. Since then, a relatively extensive amount of complex research and theories have been assembled under its label. Its history has undergone a fair number of transformations and transitions. The significant phases that marked its history were discussed in depth accounting for the different points in the history of 'geo-politics' in a volume titled: *Geopolitical Traditions: A century of geopolitical thought*, edited by David Atkinson and Klaus Dodds (2003). Geo-politics as new term ushered a new type of research and study for a new era. Its focal objective is to offer a new understanding and conceptualization of the geographical and relational networks of the world's nation states (Heffernan 27). Among the studies conducted at the beginning of its development we find researchers such as Ó Tuathail 1996; Holdar 1992; Raffestin, Lopreno and Pasteur, 1995. Like any other discipline in its inception, a coherent and well-defined body of knowledge to geo-politics from theory to a ground application linking the local to the global was absent. Essentially, the term emerged as a substitute to a prior existing intellectual enterprise under the label of political geography. Nevertheless, geo-politics was not introduced as a direct substitute to political geography, rather, such novelty in the discipline sought to introduce a new account to the preexisting and fundamentally

unexamined geo-political dimensions in the political world (Atkinson, Dodds18). Beyond the historical space of geo-politics, my chief concern, in this paper, is to provide insight into the current points of emphasis of research on geopolitics. Principally, bibliometric analysis will be employed with the objective of mapping the current state of the arts in geo-political research.

Bibliometrics as a term is of recent origin. It was coined by Pritchard in 1969. Before 1969, such analysis had no title at all, and sometimes called "statistical bibliography". With initial attempts comprised of statistical methods for the study of different subjects. However, its usage and practical application can be traced back all the way to the 1890s. Essentially, the term bibliometric analysis is defined as a statistical evaluation of published scientific research found in books, journal papers, and other research articles (Sengupta 75-98). The main objective of bibliometric analysis is an extensive mapping of the amount of literature produced in all disciplines and body of knowledge; accounting for the number of publications, the number of citations, the number of authors (individual or group), the co-authorship between authors, the key words used and repeated vocabulary. Research on literature analysis was studied quantitatively dating back to the early 20th century with some of the most important works including F.J. Cole and N.B. Ayers, in 1917, when they first studied the literature of comparative anatomy published from 1543-1860, using a quantitative analysis method. In 1923, E.W. Hume introduced "documentary statistics" as a title. Lastly, in 1969, A. Pritchard, a philologist, proposed to replace "documentary statistics" with bibliometrics as an all-encompassing research of literature statistics from journals, books, to all sorts of publications (Zhang). Fundamentally, bibliometric analysis maps existing literature to provide a report on the state of the art in a specific discipline, and its intersections with other neighboring fields of inquiry. The main objective is to provide a comprehensive overview on the research, identifying gaps or disregarded areas to offer recommendations for both future research and practice.

Based on such objectives, this paper aims to systematically provide the latest account and research development in the geo-political field.

2. Literature Review

Geopolitical research being a multidisciplinary field has had its fair, though limited share of reviews over the years. The few studies on trends in geopolitical research were Investigated relying on different types of analysis; bibliometric analysis, content analysis, systematic literature reviews, reviews mapping, within a delineated time frame. Classifying the literature and documenting the progress as well as content of academic production is essential to uncovering the potential disparities between academics and geopoliticians struggling to assert themselves. In *Geopolitical maps: a sketch history of a neglected trend in cartography* by Edoardo. Borian, 2008, two different practices to knowledge production were uncovered. In this study, Borian asserted “the importance of the cartographic medium in representing phenomena, as well as the courage to experiment with innovative technical solutions and to reclaim a role for cartography as an important mode of expression geopolitical maps” highlighting the competition between academics and geopoliticians (E. Boria 305). Another similar research mapped the geopolitics of the Russian federation where the federal assembly addresses of Putin and Medvedev which builds upon previous research on American state-of-the-union and Russian geopolitics by examining how the Kremlin has represented Russia's geographic and geopolitical position in the post-Soviet era. This study analyzed presidential addresses to the Federal Assembly from 2000 to 2011. In addition to exploring general trends evident in these speeches, it was found that the legacies of the Cold War-era perceptions of threat, as well as dissatisfaction with the Cold War's resolution, remain salient in these speeches. However, there is some movement toward a broadening of Russia's cognitive map. (Ambrosio, Vandrovec). In the field of education, memories, models and mapping of the impact of geopolitical changes on comparative studies in education investigated the progress of international geopolitical research between the years 1996 to 2015, by

Song, D Lu, Liang, Wang, and Lin. The paper systematically reviewed the trends of geopolitical research, including the borders and the territory, global geo-culture and geo-economics, Chinese models of geopolitics etc. The study recommended that Chinese geopolitical studies should reinforce the status of geographical space and scale, through the use of the process of description, as well as integrate humanistic thoughts, to further enrich the theories and practices of geopolitical research.

A similar bibliometric and literature review analysis was carried out in evaluation of one belt one road publications by MF Bashir, B Ma; Y Qin; and Bashir. It was concluded from the research that although OBOR initiative has received considerable grasp, a bibliometric study on this topic is still lacking. Additionally, while contributions to the geopolitical literature have gradually increased over the years, and Chinese scholars are increasingly making contributions to the geopolitical literature, a study on the "Gaps in Chinese geopolitical research." *Political Geography* in 2017, uncovers a visible epistemological gap in understandings of Chinese geopolitics between voices from inside and outside China. Therefore, it was argued that "Chinese geographers should contribute more to the exploration of internal geopolitical vocabularies and theories, and furthermore translate and introduce them out of China, so that it is plausible to construct a link between scholars in China and from the rest of the world" (An, Ning, Xiaomei Cai, Hong Zhu 136-138).

Recently, critical geopolitics appears to be the main area of geopolitical research, especially with its embeddedness with humanistic (emotional, feminism) politics. In a paper titled "Progress in international geopolitical research from 1996 to 2015." (2017). The trends of geopolitical research were systematically reviewed, including global geo-culture and geo-economics, Chinese models of geopolitics, resource conflicts and ecological politics, as well as emotional geopolitics. (Song, Tao, et al. 497-512). Another article titled "Geopolitical assemblages and complexity." *Progress in Human Geography* (2014) proposed a framework for considering materiality in the field of geopolitics: assemblage and complexity theories. Drawing on literatures

beyond the field to imagine a posthuman geopolitics. The study argued for ‘a relational ontology that emphasizes the complex interactions among the elements of an assemblage’ which carries direct implications for the understandings of agency, subjectivity, and systemic change (Dittmer, Jason 385-401).

3. Objective and Research Questions

Geo-political research has gained momentum over the years. In tandem with advances in communication technologies and technology in general, geo-politics seeks to operate with the conviction that the new world being a ‘small village’ needs to be understood and accounted for from a micro and macro perspectives, in its entirety, as an integrated global whole. Consequently, a single operating system naturally needs a single all-encompassing discipline capable of capturing its complexity in providing a full view of its continuous ever-changing state. Evidently, the field of geo-politics is linked to various interrelated disciplines and new research avenues are revealed continuously. Hence, the state of the art of geo-politics is in need of continuous review and analyses to gain a wider and accurate perspective on its future search in various domains of inquiry and application. Various scholars and geographers sought refuge in this novel discipline despite the occasional criticism of this intellectual field. Geo-politics’ magnetisms offer a privileged insight into the world’s geo-political affairs. Accordingly, a thorough and continuous review of every field is vital in the mapping and scrutiny of the impact, relevance, limitations and gaps that are with no doubt present in all areas of thinking. In particular, what concerns us more here in this paper, is the advancement of geo-political research, its impact, relevance, and limitations with special regard to its intersections with other related or unrelated neighboring fields of inquiry. This paper aims, despite its restricted space, to cover the objective in mapping trends in geo-political research between 2000-2021. To cover these objectives, the following research questions led the inquiry:

- Who are the most cited authors in the field?
- Which journals have the largest number of articles in geo-political research?

- What is the leading field in terms of publications in geo-political research?
- What are the chosen methodological approaches in geo-political studies?
- What are the most frequently used key words in geo-political research?
- What terms occur most frequently within the research?
- What is the highest amount of co-authorship between countries in distance language education?
- What is the highest amount of co-authorship between authors in the geo-political discipline?

4. Research Methodology

For this research overview, I developed a search strategy to identify the relevant literature. This search strategy was allotted to one of the most widely used databases: Scopus and the search terms used were the following: “Geopolitics” AND “Research”. The search spanned from the database year 2000 until 2021, though present 2021 research was not yet finalized at the time of extraction, an inclusion was necessary for a complete and comprehensive assessment addressing possible measurements for the relevant questions only. The Scopus search engine was used between 2000 and 2021 to identify broad literature in geopolitical discipline. Scopus is one of the most extensive citations and abstract databases of peer-reviewed literature from scientific journals, books, to conference proceedings. The search string was limited to obtain the most appropriate record on publication years 2000-2021. The initial search identifies publication related to geopolitics AND Research 23,196 document results. The search was then limited to the relevant period from 2000 to 2021 and revealed 6,343 document results. After limitations the search revealed 4,358 document results. In their titles, abstract, or keywords: geopolitical AND research AND (limit-to "all"). The query was limited-to (OA, "publisher full gold"). It was limited-to (pub Year, 2000). limited-to (pub stage, "final") AND (limit-to (doctype, "article") and limited-to (doctype, "review") limit-to (doctype, "conference proceedings"). Limit-to (doctype,

"book series") limit-to (doctype, "journal") limit-to (doctype, "books")) and (limit-to (language, "English")) and (limit-to (source type, "journal") AND (limit-to (subject area, "sociology") and limit-to (subject area, "environment") AND limit-to (subject area, "economics") limit-to (subject area, "arts") limit-to (subject area, "computer science") limit-to (subject area, "multidisciplinary").

4.1. Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

The search was guided by a systemic review approach coupled with a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria used to filter irrelevant results to the objectives of the query of the bibliometric search. Accordingly, publications on geopolitical researches in different international journals were obtained comprised of open access publication only between the year (2000-2021). This includes the following items: book chapters, books, reviews, conference proceedings, journal articles, conference reviews, and editorials. The search results used a language limitation to publications in the English language only with no geographical restrictions. In addition, based on the identification of publications and subject area, only those that precisely concentrated on geopolitical research in isolation or with intersections with other disciplines were included. Furthermore, prior to extraction, duplicate records were omitted before the data extraction stage to extract relevant data only capable of meaningfully informing the analysis process.

4.2. Data Extraction and Analysis

At the extraction stage, the results obtained at the end of the search were saved into visualized output results in Scopus. The extracted data were imported into excel sheets where several categories were organized based on each relevant category of obtained data. VOS viewer has been primarily utilized as a visualization program for the imported data to establish network and maps based on collected data. The data was categorized according to many variables; most cited authors based on citation metrics, top journals, types of publications, number of publication per area, number of

publications per research areas, type of methodologies employed, most frequently used key words, identifying networks based on co-authorship between authors and co-authorship between countries, most active discipline in terms of quantity of output research produced, the multidisciplinary studies conducted in intersection with the geo-political field. Using VOS viewer, the imported data was organized in network maps and links were created to showcase the publications’ links based on commonly used keywords within publication titles and abstracts (co-occurrence), an assessment of (co-authorship) between authors, and (co-citation). The bibliometric analysis helped identify the research trends of geo-politics in various disciplines: Agricultural and Biological Sciences Arts and Humanities, Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology, Business, Management and Accounting Chemical Engineering, Chemistry, Computer Science, Decision Sciences, Earth and Planetary Sciences, Economics, Econometrics and Finance, Energy, Engineering, Environmental Science, Health Professions, Immunology and Microbiology, Materials Science, Mathematics, Medicine, Multidisciplinary, Neuroscience, Physics and Astronomy, Psychology, Social Sciences.

5. Results and Interpretation

Figure 1: Publication distribution by year.

Figure 2: Publication distribution by year.

Figure 3: Publication distribution by country/Territory.

Figure 4: Publication’s by author.

Figure 5: Records distribution by subject area.

Journals	Number of publications
Sustainability Switzerland	185
Plos One	86
Political Geography	86
Iop Conference Series Earth and Environmental Science	76
Geopolitics	69
E3s Web of Conferences	40
Progress In Human Geography	38
International Journal of Environmental Research and Public	33

Health	
International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy	30
Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences	30
Geoforum	27
Resources Policy	26
Russia In Global Affairs	24
Research In International Business and Finance	19
Environment And Planning D Society and Space	18
Environment And Planning A	17
Energy Research and Social Science	16
Territory Politics Governance	15

Table 1: Journals with most publication records per year.

Table 1 classifies the journals with the highest number of yearly publications from 2000-2021. The leading journal is Sustainability Switzerland with 185 publications per year, followed by Plos One with 86 publications per year.

The extracted data set of the selected empirical studies on geo-political research focused on various topics of all journals in Scopus database; most notably the ones with the highest number of publications per year (figure 2) and type of publication (figure 1). Specifically, most studies conducted between the periods of 2000-2021 have increased considerably throughout the years. The Preliminary data set revealed studies consisting of 3619 articles, 112 book chapters, 214 conference papers, 66 books, 65 editorials, 282 reviews which focused on advancement and amount of production in the field of geo-political studies. However, only few publications addressed the state of the art of geo-political research to document its development and intersection with other neighboring fields of enquiry. Mapping trends in geo-political research over the years plays a significant impact on the way authors and academia in general are fully invested in political analysis tracing steps taken and drawing on links and networks in the world's geo-political arena; the way policy-makers think, the amount of state-to state cooperation, on the one hand, and

academical co-authorship and cooperation between scholars on the other. After the year of 2000, a significant increase in number of publications in the field from 2 in the year 2000 to 883 in 2021. A growing focus on geo-political research on the part of policy makers and academics recognizing the extent of its reach and influence in dealing with international politics and welfare systems that bare a direct effect on each and every citizen with grand implications on either future peace or warfare possibilities. Subsequently, and especially what followed with worldwide health crisis, the increase in trajectories can be, with outmost certainty, predicted to continue and expand much faster in the near future.

When it comes to the documents production by country or area in the third figure and within the same selected year range, we notice that the leading country in terms of articles and conference papers production per year is headed by the United Kingdom. The geo-political research production in various journals of different studies is geographically irregular, where the number of publications in some countries significantly exceeds others. The United Kingdom leads geo-political research production with 1082 from the year range 2000-2021. Followed with a relatively far second position by the United States with an amount of production of 730. In the far east we find the Russian Federation right after the US with 364, and China with a high policy research with 292 publications. Germany (267), Australia (221), Canada (178), Netherlands (174), France (151), South Africa (142), Poland (140), Sweden (137), Finland (120), Italy (120), Spain (113), Norway (110), Nigeria (107), Turkey (101), Switzerland (86), Belgium (84), Brazil (75), Czech Republic (66), Japan (66), India (64). This reflects the most powerful nations' interest and focus on geo-political research considering its powerful and significant impact on their future development and influence in world's politics.

The fourth figure displays the authors published articles in different international journal associated with geopolitical research. The documents' distribution by author shows the number of articles produced by year per author within the same time frame.

The author with most productions per year is Gupta, R. Dr. Rangan. Gupta works currently as a Professor at the Department of Economics, University of Pretoria, South Africa with 32 publications (Books and Articles) per year and 20597 citations. Followed by Su, Chi.Wei with 1 860 citations and 13 publications per year. Bouri, Ellie, with 7,004 citations, is an associate professor of Finance at the School of Business at the Lebanese American University with (12) publications per year. Sonnemann, G. with 124 highly influential citations in semantic scholar and 145 scientific research papers with (11) publications per year. Asongu, S.A. (10), Bilgin, P. (10), Dittmer, J. (10), Ge, Y. Kallio, K.P. Müller, M. Wohar, M.E. (9), Bach, V. Gkillas, K. Katsanevakis, S. (8), Helbig, C. Jurajda, P. Kark, S. Levin, N. Pierdzioch, C. Qin, M. Tao, R. (7). Basham, V.M. Berger, M. Bonato, M. Demirer, R. Doucette, J. (6). The volume of authors in geopolitical related research is centered within a relatively small group of scholars working in a few academic institutions that operate through interdepartmental collaborations as well as in international co-authorship collaborations.

Figure 5 displays documents distribution by subject area with the highest number of articles and conference papers production per year headed by the Social Sciences with 3066 publications from 2000-2021. Environmental Science with 1130, Economics, Econometrics and Finance (773), Arts and Humanities (751), Earth and Planetary Sciences (428), Business, Management and Accounting (317), Agricultural and Biological Sciences (251), Computer Science (216), Multidisciplinary (180), Engineering (167), Medicine (98), Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology (82), Psychology (76). Geopolitical research is a multidisciplinary field of inquiry that encompasses aspects from neighboring disciplines with the geo aspect Earth and Planetary Sciences, Agricultural and Biological Sciences. The politics part gathers disciplines primarily the social sciences as a leading category, Business, Management and Accounting, multidisciplinary, Engineering, Computer Science, psychology. Accordingly, geopolitical research would naturally gravitate towards the social

sciences that focuses essentially on topics connected to human behavior in relation to society and culture and organizations at large including political issues at the center.

Figure 6: Network of cooperation: co-authorship between countries.

A full counting with a maximum number of counties per document is 10. Minimum number of documents of a country is 5. Minimum number of citations of a country is 1. Of the 164 countries, 70 met the threshold. For each of the 70 countries, the total strength of the co-authorship links with other countries was calculated. The countries with the greatest total links strength were selected. Number of countries selected is 70. The map illustrates the network of cooperation and co-authorship between countries. Based on how frequently the co-authorship occurs in the imported data to the software, the publications being the nodes which represent linkages that denote co-authorship relationships. Larger node signifies the highest amount of co-authorship between countries; meaning, the countries with the biggest number of cooperation internationally. Publications with more occurrences will display a link strength indicated by thick threads attached to the nodes. Nodes are colored depending on the wide-ranging frequency with which the cooperation occurs in a publication in the specified time frame; with the most recent publications given precedence and colored lighter than their darker old counterparts.

Figure 7: Cooperation network: co-authorship between authors.

The maximum numbers of authors per document was limited to 25 authors with a full count. With the minimum number of documents for an author 2 publications. As for the minimum number of citations of an author is 0. Of the 5122 authors, 447 met the threshold. For each of the 447 authors, the total link strength of co-authorship with other authors was calculated. The authors with the greatest total link strength were selected with a total number of 447. The map illustrates the network of cooperation network (co-authorship between authors), based on how frequently the co-authorship occurs in the imported data to the software. After the refinement of the search, the publications are represented by the nodes which represent linkages and denote co-authorship relationships. The larger node signifies the highest amount of co-authorship between authors; signaling publications with the biggest number of co-authorships internationally. Publications with more author collaborations will display a link strength indicated by thick threads attached to the nodes. The nodes are colored depending on the wide-ranging frequency with which the cooperation occurs in a publication. The most recent publications are prioritized and colored lighter than the darker old nodes.

default choice was to select the 60% most relevant terms. Of a full counting of 42710 terms, 989 met the threshold. Minimum number of occurrences of a term is 10. The Number of terms selected is 593. Both figures illustrate the co-occurrence of all key words and terms in authors title and abstract fields based on how frequently they occur in the same publications. Based on how frequently the key words occur in the imported data to the software, and after refinement of the search, the key words are represented by the nodes. Nodes are colored depending on the frequency with which they occur in a publication. Link strength denote the co-occurrence frequency. The keywords that occur more frequently and with more publications are clustered together and are colored significantly brighter considering their occurrence in various publications compared to other fading and past publications over the delineated time frame.

6. Discussion

Co-authorship between countries in figure 6 shows a collaboration map between major countries based on co-authorship of their authors. The different colors represent the different clusters formed by the group of countries and the circle sizes to constitute the number of articles per country. The bigger the circle or node of each country, the higher number of publications based on co-authorship between countries. Cluster 1, the largest, includes the United Kingdom being the biggest circle and country that collaborates to co-authorship with other countries with an average of 393 publications and 2256 citations. Followed by the United States with a total of 273 and 990 citations. Russian Federation 218 publications and 428 citations. China 188 publications and 1096 citations. Germany with 127 and 533 cites. Canada 80 publications and 356 citations. France 74 publications and 570 citations. Australia 75 publications and 325 citations. Poland 75 publications and 308 citations. South Africa 67 publications with 311 citations. Netherlands 71 publications with 449 citations. Furthermore, Co-authorship between authors displayed in figure 7 shows a collaboration map between major authors based on co-authorship with other authors.

The different colors represent the different clusters formed by the group of authors or one author and the circle size constitute the number of articles per author in co-authorship with other authors. The bigger the circle of each country, the higher number of publications based on co-authorship between the countries. Cluster 1, Gupta. R 19 publications and 180 citations. Followed by Su. C. Wei with 13 publications and 67 citations. Wang. J 12 publications and 56 citations. Bouri. El 11 publications and 76 citations. Sonnemann. G 7 publications 106 citations. Tao. R 7 publications and 43 citations. Zhang. X 7 publications 36 citations. Qin. M with 7 publications and 54 citations.

One major observation that can be deduced from the list of co-authorship between authors and cooperation between countries in geopolitical research is the predominance of Asian names, German, Russian and English in the networks. Being the leading countries in terms of number of publications in the discipline, it should come as no surprise to see that their occupation of first positions is based on cooperation between leading countries in the field. Additionally, the leading authors in geopolitical research linked to the number of productions per year and extensive number of citations centers around their international collaborations. Furthermore, this was, in a large part, a major strategy implemented by the leading states which saw a significant increase in recent year. With advancement of information technology and globalization, the prime objective was to adopt measures for extreme vigilance tracing and mapping the networks of the world's constantly shifting politics. The competition and ambition to become leaders in the industry drove their decisions with regard to a change in the dynamic of communication and collaboration with co-authorship in academia as example in the collaboration network provided in the displayed figures.

The bibliometric analysis employed in this research focused on published academic studies in geopolitical discipline, with the outputs produced internationally and with English language as medium. Nevertheless, a relatively small number of academic researchers in the field in different international journals explicitly investigated the

research trends of geopolitical research. Furthermore, the lack of mapping for the field is not new to other fields of enquiry, however, it is prevalent especially in geopolitical studies. The mapping and systematic review of existing literature is a necessary applied component of the social and political sciences, economic, and multidisciplinary studies. This latter presents a more complex interrelatedness between knowledge production, evaluation and power. The development and progress in geopolitical research produce a continuous stream of new problems and prescribed solutions when available. Nonetheless, its progress has been criticized for its lack of a well-defined theory and methodology. Still, it remains a vibrant and focal actor in world politics and academia with leading figures and states eminent in various global sectors. In areas that are highly dependent on geopolitical research, social science, science and technology, agriculture, energy, health, and security. Differences in the geopolitical research geographical distribution production are interesting. Certain countries, which happen to be powerful countries worldwide, show a substantially extensive yearly production and overall higher performance compared to others. On the other hand, geopolitical studies in general are far more prevalent in some fields and appear to surpass others in certain journal collections. Moreover, geopolitical research is arranged within a relatively small set of academics within the diverse associations and academia's research groups that exist internationally. Additionally, while a small portion of research produced in the field of the study showed multidisciplinary with 3%, there is little theoretical bridging between contemporary studies in geopolitics due to the lack of a robust theoretical and methodological grounding and collaboration between authors globally. Thus, to solve most of the field's problems, the demand for ever more knowledge mapping and assessment is vital for an effective building of a geopolitical research structure.

7. Conclusion and Future Implication

To conclude, this study explored the current trends in the field of geopolitical research published between the periods of 2000 and 2021. An extensive overview of research was conducted reviewing all journals in Scopus dataset. A total of 4,358 publications were extracted initially according to relevance and pertinence criterion, and later on refined for 990 articles for thorough the bibliometric analysis. Principally, the bibliometric analysis was employed with the objective of mapping the current state of the arts in geopolitical research. The study identifies the most frequently cited authors and most commonly used keywords and terms and journals with highest number of publications in studies on geopolitics. The research areas were identified with the social sciences taking the lead in the field proximately followed by environmental science, arts and humanities discipline with other disciplines with a minimum number of publications.

The study presented a descriptive macro-level bibliometric analysis identifying the highest amount of research produced in journals, the greatest number of collaborations between countries, the leading countries in terms of publications, citations and co-authorship between authors, the distribution of publications by subject area, the most widely used key terms by researchers in the field of geopolitical research. In terms of the field's intersection with other disciplines, more work is needed to identify the causes and provide solutions for the minimum amount of interdisciplinarity with neighboring fields of similar inquiries and objectives. This latter would immensely enrich the conceptual background and provide limitless avenues for a more refined and effectively applied geopolitical research. Additionally, the collaboration in terms of co-authorship between authors and counties is a golden asset for any field of inquiry and especially geopolitics.

The findings of this research showed a significant increase in the number of yearly publications, especially for the past five years. Such rise can be attributed to the adverse international political atmosphere, with conflicts in different regions of the globe. Additionally, geopolitical research is mostly concentrated in countries either

involved in the conflicts or heavily invested in geopolitical research like UK, US, Russia, China, and Turkey. Accordingly, the majority of the most cited authors are from Asia and the previously mentioned countries. The results of this study contribute to the existing and prospective literature by shedding light on previously untapped avenues which would immensely enrich any potential enquiry in the field. Research in geopolitics has been consistently produced and concentrated in specific parts of the world. Hence, it ought to expand and extend its reach with more international collaborations, and by interacting with other neighboring disciplines acquiring multidimensional lenses.

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